

Full paper

SiGe nanowire arrays based thermoelectric microgenerator

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ABSTRACT

Thermoelectric micro/nanogenerators (μ TEGs) are potential candidates as energy harvesters to power IoT sensors. This study reports on a thermoelectric micro/nanogenerator with a planar architecture built by silicon micromachining technologies that uses silicon-germanium (SiGe) nanowire (NW) arrays as thermoelectric material. The growth of bottom-up NW arrays by means of Chemical Vapour Deposition - Vapour Liquid Solid growth (CVD-VLS) and their monolithic integration into prefabricated microplatforms are presented. It is shown that SiGe NWs based μ TEGs can harvest $7.1 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ without any additional heat exchanger, when there is a waste heat source available at a temperature of 200°C . Since the required power density for many sensing applications is in the range of $10\text{--}100 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ the results obtained in this work are close to meet expectations.

1. Introduction

Internet of Things (IoT) has started to spread rapidly in the last few years and is expected to gain further recognition as *the Next Industrial Revolution*. According to BI Intelligence, there will be more than 55 billion IoT devices on Earth by 2025 [1]. For the successful realization of IoT devices on several applications, they should be smart, autonomous, miniaturized, and they should have low-energy wireless communication capabilities to be able to collect data from all kinds of locations. The use of environmental energy harvesting can assist in powering IoT sensors, extending battery lifetime or even eliminate the need for batteries. Considering the low-power requirements for wireless sensor nodes of IoT ($10\text{--}100 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$) the efforts are focused on microsystem based energy harvesting [2]. Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) based energy harvesting has been attracting profound interest in the research and scientific community since its technology allows mass production, miniaturization and easy integration with electronics [3]. In addition, the repeatability and high reliability of MEMS batch fabrication processes reduce the unit cost, contributing positively to their use for IoT devices.

Environmental thermal energy can be harvested by means of thermoelectric generators, which convert heat into electricity with long operational lifetimes and reliability, and do not include any moving

parts. The efficiency of thermal-to-electrical conversion is about $\sim 5\%$ and increases with the dimensionless figure of merit of the thermoelectric material, defined as $ZT = S^2\sigma T/\kappa$, with S being the Seebeck coefficient, σ the electrical conductivity, κ the thermal conductivity, and T the average temperature between the cold and hot surfaces [4]. Considering the large amount of waste heat produced in our daily life, harvesting at least a small fraction would mean a tremendous amount of power that could be used for several applications. Most of the pioneering works reporting thermoelectric generators have focused on chalcogenide based materials, e.g. Bi_2Te_3 , which are currently employed in commercial modules with maximum figure of merit ZT of ~ 1 at room temperature. Several novel high ZT materials have also been studied, but so far their integration into generators has not yet been deeply investigated. These materials are generally not compatible with silicon MEMS technology, which is a promising way to fabricate miniaturized, low cost generators for low power IoT sensors.

Silicon-germanium (SiGe) alloys are well established thermoelectric materials for high temperature applications and have been used in Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generators (RTG) in space missions, e.g. in Voyager probes, in which they are still reliably operating after near 40 years [5]. In their crystalline bulk form these alloys possess a power factor similar to that of Si ($S^2\sigma = 40\text{--}50 \mu\text{W}/\text{K}\cdot\text{cm}$) but a reduced κ due to the alloy-induced scattering of high frequency phonons (down to

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Fig. 1. Microfabrication steps of the proposed μ TEG. a) Starting SOI substrate, b) nitride deposition and patterning, c) extra doping of Si device of SOI to decrease the Si/metal contact resistance, d) deposition and patterning of metal layer (Ti+W) via lift-off, e) passivation deposition and lithography for thinning the oxide on the contact layer, f) photolithography and dry etch of oxide to make the opening for KOH etch, g) backside DRIE for opening the bulk cavity and topside KOH etch to define and release the suspended microplatform, h) final image of the μ TEG after the integration of NWs.

$\kappa = 4$ W/m·K for a highly doped n-type $\text{Si}_{0.7}\text{Ge}_{0.3}$ alloy with respect to 150 W/m·K for pure Si) achieving a maximum ZT of 1 at 1100 K [6]. Further κ reduction can be attained by nanostructuring, which yields to enhanced phonon boundary scattering effect in nanowires, thin films, superlattices and finely-grained bulk with characteristic sizes below ~ 100 nm [7]. Boundary scattering mostly affects phonons of intermediate frequencies, leading to a drastically reduced thermal conductivity ruled by a rather small population of low frequency phonons impervious to this mechanism [8–10]. The reduction of κ by means of alloying and nanostructuring is attained without prejudice of S and σ , leading to an overall increase in ZT , as demonstrated for many thermoelectric materials including Si and SiGe nanowires and other structures [11–13]. This fact is explained by the comparatively shorter mean free path of electrons with respect to that of phonons in doped semiconductors, which is not reduced in a large proportion when boundary and point-defect (i.e. alloying) disruptions of lattice periodicity are introduced. In the case of SiGe nanowires (NWs) a minimum κ of 1–2 W/m·K and a maximum ZT of 0.46 at 450 K (two times that of similar composition bulk alloy) were reported [14]. Since alloying significantly increases the raw material cost (Ge 900 \$/kg vs. Si 1 \$/kg), nanostructuring can be regarded as an approach to reduce the amount of Ge needed to yield the targeted ZT (e.g. from 20% to 5% for a ZT of 0.9 as in [15]), as well as increasing the power per unit mass [16,17].

Importantly and differently from the above mentioned chalcogenides, silicon-based materials as SiGe exhibit an excellent compatibility with micro-fabrication techniques, which are based in processing of Si wafers, and have been regularly used in thin film form for the formation of ultra-fast strained BiCMOS channels and low-resistive contacts [18]. Achieving a fully micro-technology compatible fabrication of the μ TEG enables to easily scale-up the number of thermocouples interconnecting on-chip as many of them as needed and, moreover, to directly integrate the final devices together with the targeted low-power electronics, reducing costs. In this sense, technology-compatible approaches for both μ TEG device and nanomaterial fabrication and integration must be carefully designed to this end. For pure Si thermoelectric micro-devices, integration has been achieved in several cases with nanowires, thin films and nanobulk silicon [19–31], whereas for SiGe it has only been

attained for thin films [32–35]. Although Si nanostructures and SiGe thin films present demonstrated thermoelectric properties, SiGe NWs show an even further enhanced ZT , due to the combined effects of alloy-induced phonon scattering (not present in Si) and increased phonon boundary scattering with respect to thin films [35].

This work reports for first time the fabrication and characterization of a SiGe NW-based thermoelectric microgenerator (μ TEG) fully obtained using MEMS technology with the aim of powering low-power electronic devices as wireless sensor nodes for IoT applications. Results on μ TEG design, micro-fabrication, integration of SiGe NW arrays, and thermoelectric performance of the device are presented and discussed.

2. Strategy of the μ TEG

The idea behind the proposed thermoelectric microgenerator (μ TEG), which is merging top-down silicon micromachining technology with bottom-up nanowire (NW) growth, was first presented by Davila et al. [21,36]. In those studies, monolithic integration of Si NWs grown by Chemical Vapour Deposition - Vapour Liquid Solid growth (CVD-VLS) into microtrenches was reported. Next, the microplatform design was improved to enhance the thermal isolation between the hot and cold parts and to reduce the internal electric resistance [37]. In this work, an ulterior evolution of the device is undertaken by integrating SiGe NWs in a further optimized microplatform.

Top-down micromachining techniques on silicon on insulator (SOI) substrates are used to fabricate a microplatform composed of a suspended Si platform (device layer of the SOI wafer) poorly thermally linked to a surrounding Si rim (full bulk of the SOI wafer). This architecture allows that hot and cold junctions coexist in a planar thermoelectric device. Thus, when placed on a waste heat source, the suspended platform and the bulk Si rim act as a cold side and a hot side of the generator, respectively. After completing the fabrication of the microplatform, p-type SiGe NW arrays have been integrated laterally by a bottom-up method (CVD-VLS) between the isolated suspended platform and the Si rim. It is worth noticing that the proposed device requires the sides of the microplatform to be aligned to vertical < 111 > walls which is the preferential orientation for NWs growth. For

Fig. 2. SEM image of the fabricated μ TEG. Images are colored to clarify functions of each structures: built-in thermometer (green), internal collector (yellow), external collector (orange), and thermometer (red).

this reason, the device layer of the starting SOI wafer features a (110) orientation.

For technological simplicity, our planar μ TEG is fabricated employing a uni-leg architecture, in which the thermocouple is formed by a semiconductor thermoelectric material (p-type SiGe NW arrays, on three sides of the platform) and a metal layer (Ti+W on the remaining side of the platform). The proposed architecture for the single thermocouple is easily scalable to parallel or serial connections in order to increase the current or voltage, respectively, of the final micro-generator. Fig. 1 illustrates the microfabrication steps for a single thermocouple of the proposed μ TEG which is detailed in the supporting information. Since the single thermocouple is already producing power, we may indistinctly refer to it also as a μ TEG in this paper, although strictly speaking, the μ TEG will be the result of replicating on-chip that unitary thermocouple in series/parallel arrangements.

Fig. 2 shows a colored SEM image of the basic thermocouple of the proposed μ TEGs to clarify the functions of different device parts. It includes a built-in temperature sensor (green) which can be used as a heater to dissipate power for in-situ test purposes, and internal/external collectors (yellow/orange) to measure the Seebeck voltage, device resistance, and the final thermoelectric power output. In addition, a second thermometer (red) is included to be able to measure the temperature of the bulk Si rim. The suspended platform is connected to the bulk Si rim through a thin dielectric membrane to act as a microplatform mechanical support and as a holder for the thermocouple metal leg. The definition of this membrane requires a dedicated processing step since the high thermal conductivity Si beneath the dielectric thin film needs to be removed. For that purpose, the membrane structure has been designed with a saw pattern, with proper angles to enable fast Si lateral removal under the membrane using an anisotropic KOH wet etch.

Fig. 3. a) Steps for NW growth and integration in μ TEGs. Left: Si trenches exposing the $\langle 111 \rangle$ planes with oxide-passivated top part. Middle: Au NPs are selectively deposited in Si by means of galvanic displacement (an electroless redox process in liquid phase) followed by a thermal annealing step. Right: SiGe NWs are grown epitaxially from Au NPs by means of a CVD-VLS process. b) formation of a monolithic connection once the nanowire reaches the opposite trench wall. The characteristic angle of 71° between integrated and “rebounding” NWs corresponds to the angle between different directions of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ family. c) Si NW in a $\langle 111 \rangle$ Si trench device similar to those employed in present μ TEGs, with a 71° angle indicating monolithic integration, extracted from [41].

To optimise the power output of the μ TEG different effective lengths of the NWs were analysed. For this, devices with different number of consecutive trenches (1–4, referred as T1-T4) are designed between suspended platform and the rim. The trenches are defined by intermediate perimeter silicon bars. Trench width is designed to be $10 \mu\text{m}$ to cope with some constraints of the NW growth method and to avoid long deposition times. The trench depth is set by the thickness of the Si device layer of SOI substrate, which is chosen to be $15 \mu\text{m}$ to accommodate a large number of NWs. Additionally, $10 \mu\text{m}$ long Si bars are defined as well in the corners of the active area of the device connecting the thermally isolated platform to bulk Si rim (parallel to the NWs) to provide robustness to the device before NW growth. These bars are cut using focused ion beam (FIB) after the NW growth to prevent parasitic thermal paths between hot and cold ends of the device as will be shown later.

3. Integration of SiGe NWs

Boron-doped SiGe NWs were grown and integrated in device micro-trenches by means of gold-catalyzed VLS method, as illustrated in Fig. 3a [38,39]. Briefly, gold nanoparticles (Au NPs) were first selectively deposited on silicon trenches by means of a surfactant-aided galvanic displacement process and then exposed to silane (SiH_4), germane (GeH_4) and diborane (B_2H_6) at 650°C and 2.5 Torr within a CVD reactor. Au NPs act as catalysts for precursor decomposition, so that Si, Ge and B atoms pass from a gas phase (SiH_4 , GeH_4 and B_2H_6 reactants within the CVD ambient) through a liquid phase (within the catalyst particles, which become an Au-Si/Ge/B liquid alloy at these conditions) to a solid phase (within the nanowire, which grows epitaxially from the $\langle 111 \rangle$ device trench walls). This method allows for the monolithic integration (Fig. 3b,c) of the nanowires yielding a low electrical and thermal contact resistance [40]. Further details of galvanic displacement and CVD-VLS conditions are given in the supporting information.

In order to obtain SiGe NWs able to successfully exploit the thermoelectric effect in μ TEG devices, the effects of the CVD parameters were studied and the growth was optimized [41]. The NWs should be grown with length $L > 10 \mu\text{m}$ for enabling integration, small diameter $d < 100 \text{ nm}$ for effective boundary scattering, proper doping level and $\text{Si}_x\text{Ge}_{1-x}$ composition ($\text{conc.} > 10^{20} \text{ B atoms/cm}^3$ for high $S^2\sigma$, and $0.2 < x < 0.8$ for effective alloy scattering), high alignment and density in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions for monolithic integration and low electrical resistance, and no concomitant ubiquitous deposition of poly-SiGe (which would cover critical parts leading to device malfunctioning) [4,13].

Fig. 4 shows NWs grown at the selected conditions on different substrates employed in the optimization study, using gold colloid deposition on [111] Si for obtaining isolated NWs, galvanic displacement

Fig. 4. SEM images of SiGe NWs and poly-SiGe obtained by the same CVD-VLS process over different substrates. a) top view of SiGe NWs grown from 80 nm Au colloids deposited onto a Si chip exposing a $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal plane. b) and c) top view and close-up cross-section, respectively, of SiGe NWs grown from a dense NP array deposited by galvanic displacement onto a Si chip exposing the $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal plane. d) poly-SiGe nanocrystals deposited onto a silicon nitride, gold-less chip. e) representation of nanowires growing epitaxially from a $\langle 111 \rangle$ substrate, following the four possible directions of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ family. While angle between nanowires is 70.5° (appreciated in perspective view, at top) the projection of the non-vertical wires when observed from above form angles of 120° (appreciated in top view, at bottom).

on [111] Si for growth of dense arrays, and silicon nitride gold-less chips for assessment of the degree of unwanted poly-SiGe deposition. The 120° angles observed in the top view of isolated NWs grown over a [111] Si substrate (Fig. 4a) correspond to the projections of NWs growing in $[\bar{1}11]$, $[1\bar{1}1]$ and $[11\bar{1}]$ directions (Fig. 4e), revealing the epitaxial nature of the growth [42]. This preferred alignment was appreciated as well in dense arrays (Fig. 4b,c). Regarding poly-SiGe deposition, a sparse pattern of NPs rather than a continuous layer was observed, unable to cover the gold-less substrates, and thus avoiding unwanted short-circuiting of device parts (Fig. 4d).

The obtained NWs featured a diameter of 64 ± 11 nm, length of 5–20 μm , composition of 30% Ge ($\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$, $x = 0.3$), and doping of $\sim 10^{20}$ B atoms/ cm^3 , as inferred by SEM and EDX and Seebeck measurements discussed below. A facile control of length attained by tuning the growth time (Fig. 5a) and the highly-selective and dense gold nanoparticle deposition in Si conferred by galvanic displacement

(Fig. 5b,c) allowed for the integration of large number of NWs in device micro-trenches, in the order of ~ 1 NW/ μm^2 (Fig. 5d).

4. TEG performance

4.1. Cutting ancillary Si support bars

To be able to keep the integrity of the suspended platform before the NW growth, short supporting Si bars are introduced across the trenches at the corners of the suspended platform. Since trenches are defined by anisotropic KOH etch, these supporting beams feature a final pyramidal shape due to the presence of $\langle 111 \rangle$ oblique planes blocking the etch. The top SEM image of Fig. 6a shows one of these corners after KOH in a device with 3 trenches. After growing the NWs, these supports are cut by focused ion beam (FIB) to prevent thermal losses through the high thermal conducting Si bars (Fig. 6a-bottom).

Fig. 5. a) Length of Si-Ge NWs as a function of growth time. After a nucleation time of ~ 10 min length increases linearly with time. b) and c) 45° tilted SEM image of device trenches after the galvanic displacement process. Au NPs were deposited only onto Si exposed at trenches and not in the top part – protected by Si_3N_4 and SiO_2 . d) Top-view SEM image of SiGe NWs selectively grown in Si exposed parts after galvanic displacement and CVD-VLS growth. A layer of disordered nanowires on the topmost part – due to gold deposition at edges – masks the aligned wires within trenches, which are not as evident as in the free area at right.

Fig. 6. a) SEM images of supporting Si bars between the corners of suspended platform and bulk Si rim for the device with 3 trenches (T3) after opening by KOH (top) and similar corner with NWs grown and bulk Si supports cut by FIB (bottom). b) Open circuit voltage obtained from the μ TEGs with different number of trenches with respect to hot plate temperature before and after cutting the Si bars with FIB.

When the heating stage used for harvesting measurements is set to a given temperature, the Seebeck voltage measured (between the internal and external collectors using a multimeter) increases after the removal of the Si bars by FIB: a larger temperature difference develops between microplatform and rim once these Si bars are cut and thus a larger open circuit voltage is generated. That means that the negative contribution of these Si bars to the thermal conductance between microplatform and surrounding rim is significant. In addition, higher voltages are always obtained for devices with larger number of trenches due to the higher thermal resistance achieved between the hot and cold sides of the microgenerator because of the increased effective NW length. A maximum Seebeck voltage of 4.14 mV is obtained from the device with four trenches at a hot plate temperature of 200 °C (Fig. 6b).

4.2. Seebeck coefficient

Seebeck coefficient of SiGe NWs is measured by calibrating the thermometer/heater on the suspended microplatform (by measuring its Temperature Coefficient of Resistance) and after Joule heating of the platform forcing a controlled current through the heater using the source meter. In other words, a known amount of power is dissipated in the isolated platform using the heater to achieve a ΔT between microplatform and silicon rim. Open circuit voltage between the internal and external collectors (at the two ends of the NWs) of the device is collected by a multimeter while forcing different ΔT (2.5, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5 K) as measured by the thermometer/heater at different ambient operation temperatures (300 – 500 K). Seebeck coefficient is calculated from the slope of V_{oc} vs ΔT curve for each of those operation temperatures.

Fig. 7 shows the variation of the Seebeck coefficient as a function of ambient temperature together with the reference data from other works for SiGe NW and bulk materials. Data for SiGe NWs are very scarce in the literature and no similar characterization to the one performed in this work was found. For both bulk and NWs, Seebeck coefficient increases with temperature. For the case of SiGe NWs, steeper increase of the Seebeck coefficient is observed compared to SiGe bulk alloys. This could be explained by the additional phonon boundary scattering mechanism introduced in the NWs. The detailed mechanism behind the change of Seebeck coefficient is under investigation on different materials by several research groups and is beyond of the scope of this work [6,43,44].

4.3. Thermoelectric power

Power curves obtained from SiGe NWs-based μ TEGs are shown in Fig. 8. Even though a maximum Seebeck voltage is obtained for the

Fig. 7. Calculated Seebeck coefficient vs temperature graph for SiGe NW arrays. The literature values are taken from Refs.[6,45].

device with four trenches (T4) as expected from its better microplatform thermal isolation, the maximum power is attained from the device with three trenches (T3). This is due to the trade-off between thermal and electrical effects in the generated power. The power obtained in a micro thermoelectric generator depends on the open circuit voltage and on the internal electric resistance ($P \approx V^2/R$). The first one is the consequence of the Seebeck transduction of the ΔT that is established across the thermoelectric material and as such depends on its Seebeck coefficient and thermal resistance. The second corresponds in our case to the sum of the nanowire, contact, and metal resistances measured between the internal and external collectors and it is a purely electric effect. Increasing the number of trenches, and hence the effective length of the NW arrays, increases both their thermal and electric resistance impacting power in opposite ways, positive and negative, respectively. Table 1 reports the resistance measured for our T2-T4 devices. Even though such resistance is expected to increase with the number of trenches (also confirmed by FEM simulations), the obtained results do not show a clear linear dependence on the effective length of the NW ensemble. The factors that may contribute to this spurious resistance difference can be the result of local processing variations, or even measuring conditions (two-wire measurements). Issues affecting device electric resistance could be metal related (silicon-metal contact resistance, process induced metal properties variation), or linked to a variation of the amount of silicon material bridging platform and rim (efficacy of the starting NWs seed coverage or density, strain-induced misalignment of the opposing areas to be filled by NWs, incomplete removal of the ancillary silicon microbeams). It should be noted that although any variation in the amount of bridging silicon material has a

Fig. 8. Current-voltage and current-power curves obtained from SiGe NWs based μTEGs with different number of trenches (a-c from T2-T4) for different hot plate temperatures.

Table 1

Harvesting parameters of SiGe NWs-based μTEG with different trench numbers for a hot plate temperature of 200 °C. Power density is calculated assuming a 2 mm² device area and load matching conditions.

	T2	T3	T4
V _{oc} (mV)	2.7	3.4	4.2
ΔT (K)	11.5	14.3	17.6
R _{device} (Ω)	22.5	19.5	53.3
Max. Power Density (μW/cm ²)	4.0	7.1	4.1

direct effect in the electric resistance, its impact in thermal resistance is lower as it is modulated by the thermal properties of air, which is the most abundant material bridging the trenches at the low NWs density regime employed. This is especially truer for low thermal conductance materials as SiGe. Indeed, the Seebeck voltages obtained show a much linear behaviour than the electric resistance values.

The maximum power obtained for the best performing device (T3) is 142 nW when the hot plate is set to 200 °C, which corresponds to a power density of 7.1 μW/cm² considering a device area of 2 mm². The latter value is an estimation for the active device area assuming that some of the device features shown in Fig. 2 (like pads and external collectors) would be shared in a high-packed chip design comprising tens of those devices linked in series or parallel. As a reference, the device as-it-is features a 3 mm² area while the microplatform itself amounts to 1 mm². The maximum ΔT attained under these conditions is estimated to be 17.6 K (T4) using the Seebeck coefficient values of the previous section. It is worth noticing that no heat exchanger has been placed on top of the device, so the poor thermal connection of the microplatform to the ambient air impedes capturing across the NWs more than 10% of the external available temperature difference (180 °C). It should be noted that similar devices populated with Si NWs captured ten times less temperature, giving evidence of the much lower intrinsic thermal conductivity of SiGe NWs [46]. This shows that the use of high thermal resistance thermoelectric materials is important in device arrangements as the present one, where the thermal resistance between heat source and heat sink is very high. In any case, the integration of a heat exchanger will further greatly increase ΔT, V_{oc} and power.

Table 2 compares the results obtained in this work with similar state-of-the-art SiGe based μTEGs reported in the literature. Most of the studies report μTEGs using thin films of SiGe as thermoelectric material due to its widely studied processing using microfabrication technologies. There is only one attempt from Imperial College to demonstrate SiGe NW arrays' output power. However, in that study, bulk Si or Si NWs were used as a n-type leg while including SiGe NW arrays as a p-type leg built by metal-assisted-chemical-etching (MACE) [47]. The attained power outputs (and power densities) were very low, which was attributed to high internal electrical resistances. For the rest of cases, comparison is challenging because ΔT values reported differ widely and the interpretation of the nature of the reported ΔT (or its physical meaningfulness) is not clear. Most of the studies reporting μTEGs specify their performance applying a ΔT to the system by means of

Table 2

Comparison of the results obtained in this work with the state-of-the-art SiGe based μTEGs.

TE material	ΔT (K)	No of couples	P _{max} /A (μW/cm ²)	P _{max} /couple (nW)	Ref.
poly SiGe	8.5	15782	2.73	0.012	[32]
Poly SiGe	29	1766	18	0.25	[34]
B-doped SiGe/ Au	–	20	–	4–13	[33]
Poly SiGe	1	278–333	–	0.006–0.007	[35]
Si/SiGe NW	3.3	1	0.00013	0.2	[47]
SiGe NW	14.3	1	7.1	142	This work

artificially dissipating a power on it, or by actively forcing a temperature difference across both ends of the device. For instance, it is difficult to comment on the ΔT achieved by researchers at AIST [33] since their μTEG included a catalyst combustor and was powered by a gas flow. In the study conducted by Infineon [32], a Peltier cooler was mounted on top of the poly SiGe based μTEGs and ΔT was defined by measuring the temperature difference over the chip. IMEC also reported on poly-SiGe based μTEGs [34,35], for which ΔT was set by placing the thermocouples in between big metal blocks that acted as heating and cooling plates, which might be closer to the real application environment. Our work demonstrates a real generic application case, in which ΔT develops naturally across the μTEG itself under the operation ambient conditions, it is unique in the way SiGe NWs are used and integrated, and compares nicely in terms of performance with previous attempts. In particular, the work presented herein reports the highest power per couple among its counterparts for the given temperature differences.

5. Conclusions

This study reports for the first time the fabrication and characterization of SiGe NWs-based μTEGs. The μTEGs are fabricated with silicon technology and feature a suspended microplatform surrounded by a bulk silicon rim (with a given number of silicon trenches in between). This architecture enables converting a vertically occurring thermal gradient into a lateral one across the gap between those two silicon regions that it is filled with the NWs. Large number of Boron-doped SiGe NWs with diameter of 64 ± 11 nm, length of 10 μm, 30% Ge content, and doping of $\sim 10^{20}$ cm⁻³ were grown simultaneously and integrated by means of gold-catalyzed CVD-VLS approach in devices with different number of micro-trenches. A maximum power of 142 nW, corresponding to a power density of 7.1 μW/cm², was obtained from a three trenches single thermocouple when it was placed on a heat source at 200 °C. The results obtained in this work for SiGe-based thermoelectric microgenerators are very promising, and point to their high potential for harvesting energy in waste heat scenarios such as Industrial Internet of Things applications.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.12.050](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.12.050).

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